

Phenolic content and enzyme activities of tea leaves

B. Srividhya^a, R. Subramanian^b and V. Raj^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, KSR College of Technology, Tiruchengode-637 215, Tamilnadu, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Periyar University, Salem-636 011, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : alaguraj2@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-427-2345124

vmhanvidhya@yahoo.co.in : 91-4288-274860

subu_m1@yahoo.com : 91-427-2345124

Manuscript received 24 May 2011, revised 12 October 2011, accepted 17 October 2011

Abstract : Total polyphenols, catechin, caffeine, reducing sugars, theaflavin (TF), thearubigin (TR), polyphenol oxidase (PPO), peroxidase (POD) and superoxide dismutase-like (SOD) activities of green and black tea were measured and compared with each other. The results indicate that total catechin, total polyphenols, reducing sugars and theaflavin of green tea were found to be higher than black tea whereas in black tea, the caffeine and thearubigin were found to be higher. Polyphenol oxidase, peroxidase and superoxide dismutase-like activity of green tea were higher than those of black tea. The results pointed to the significant biochemical parameters and enzyme activities of the green tea than black tea.

Keywords : Green tea, black tea, caffeine, polyphenol oxidase, peroxidase, superoxide dismutase-like activity.

Introduction

The growing interest in drinking tea all over the world would be connected with polyphenol antioxidative activity, fighting the harmful influence of environmentally generated free radicals¹. The rich flavonoids of tea and other polyphenols that have been shown to possess a wide range of biological and pharmaceutical benefits including anticarcinogenic antioxidative and hypolipidemic activities^{2,3}. Based on the processing, tea products are classified into non-fermented/aerated green tea, semi fermented (oolong tea) and fully fermented black tea⁴. The chemical composition of the tea includes polyphenols, purines (caffeine, theophylline and theobromine), aminoacids, carbohydrates, proteins, chlorophylls, volatile compounds, minerals and trace amounts of elements. Among these, polyphenols are the most interesting group and are the main bioactive molecules in tea⁵. The major polyphenolic compounds in tea are the flavan-3-ols : (-) epicatechin (EC), (-) epigallocatechin (EGC), (-) epicatechingallate (ECG), (-) epigallocatechingallate (EGCG), (-) galocatechins (GC) and (-) galocatechingallate (GCG). Especially catechins are present in large amount in green tea.

Tea polyphenols, in particularly catechins have shown strong antioxidant activity, especially in free radical scavenger activities viz. singlet oxygen, hydroxyl radical and

metal chelating capacity⁷. The number of free hydroxyl groups, the presence of *ortho*-hydroxylation on B-ring of flavonoid compounds, a C₂-C₃ double bond in a ring and the presence of 3-hydroxyl groups are listed as the main conditions for the antiradical and antioxidant properties⁸.

Due to presence of flavonoids, tea consumption consistently leads to a significant increase in the antioxidant capacity of the blood. The scientific support is strongest for the protection of DNA from oxidative damage after black or green tea consumption⁹. Green tea polyphenol, (-)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate is a potential anticancer agent and a *meta*-analysis of epidemiological studies indicates that consumption of green and black tea lowers the risk of breast cancer^{10,11}. Thus, regular green tea drinking might protect smokers from oxidative damages and could reduce cancer risk or other diseases caused by free radicals associated with smoking¹². Caffeine, mainly ingested by drinking coffee, cola beverages and tea act as a diuretic and as a stimulant to the central nervous and to the cardiovascular systems¹³.

The main objective of the present study is to determine the total catechins, polyphenols, reducing sugars, thearubigin, theaflavin, polyphenol oxidase, peroxidase and superoxide dismutase-like activities of green and black tea and their comparison.

Experimental

Tea samples :

Green tea and black tea samples were obtained from The United Nilgiris Tea Estate Co. Ltd., Coimbatore and Kannan Devan Tea Estate, Moonar, Kerala. The purchased tea samples were consequently subjected to analysis.

Chemicals :

(+)-Catechin was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals Private Limited, Bangalore. Pyrogallol, ascorbic acid, folin-ciocalteu's, sodium carbonate, ethyl alcohol, anthrone reagent, ferric chloride, pyrocatechol, caffeine, ethylenediaminetetracetic acid, methyl alcohol, chloroform, sodium chloride, sodium sulphate, aqueous ammonium hydroxide, (+)-dextrose and gallic acid were procured from S. D. Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India.

Tea extracts preparation :

About 2.0 g of powdered tea sample was boiled with 70% aqueous ethanol for 30 min. The extract was centrifuged and the supernatant was diluted with 100 ml distilled water and directly used for analysis.

Estimation of polyphenols :

Polyphenols in tea samples were estimated according to ISO procedure¹⁴.

Determination of catechins :

Total catechins were measured according to the literature¹⁵.

Measurement of reducing sugar :

Reducing sugar was measured according to procedure described by Hedge and Hofreiter¹⁶.

Estimation of caffeine :

Caffeine content of tea was determined according to the method of Ronald and Ronald¹⁷.

Determination of TF and TR :

TF and TR were estimated according to method described by earlier literature¹⁸.

Polyphenol oxidase activity :

PPO activity was determined according to the literature¹⁹.

Peroxidase enzyme activity :

PEO enzyme activity was measured according to literature²⁰.

Superoxide dismutase-like activity :

SOD was assayed according to the method of Marklund and Marklund²¹.

Results and discussion

Total polyphenols, catechins, reducing sugar and caffeine :

The total polyphenols, total catechins, reducing sugar and caffeine of green and black teas were given in Table 1. For comparative purpose, the result from the previous work is given in Table 2. Fig. 1 shows the comparison of biochemical parameters of green and black teas. Highest polyphenols were obtained in green tea followed by black tea, this variation in the polyphenolic composition is due to leaf maceration during manufacturing⁴. Variations in catechins of green and black teas showed clearly, the degree of fermentation during the manufacturing process has an influence on the catechin

Table 1. TP, TC, RS and CAF of green and black tea

	Green tea (%)*	Black tea (%)*
TP ^a	19.65 ± 0.14	14.07 ± 0.08
TC ^b	13.64 ± 0.03	9.59 ± 0.08
RS ^c	4.15 ± 0.05	4.30 ± 0.10
CAF ^d	1.96 ± 0.10	2.63 ± 0.15
TF ^e	0.09 ± 0.01	0.6 ± 0.1
TR ^f	6.13 ± 0.13	9.82 ± 0.06
SOD ⁱ	40.27 ± 0.46	30.33 ± 0.58
PPO ^{g*}	31.07 ± 0.01	17.9 ± 0.90
POD ^{h*}	61.23 ± 0.68	26.93 ± 0.12

*All values represent means ± S.D. of triplicate test (n = 3).

TP^a Total polyphenols; TC^b Total catechins; RS^c Reducing sugar; CAF^d Caffeine; TF^e Theaflavins; TR^f Thearubigins; PPO^{g*} Polyphenol oxidase (µM of oxygen utilized per minute per gram dry weight); POD^{h*} Peroxidase (µM of oxygen formed per minute per gram dry weight); SODⁱ Superoxide dismutase.

Table 2. Comparison of biochemical parameters among various tea samples

Tea samples	Catechins	Total phenols	Caffeine
Green tea	12-143 (25);	8.5-13.9 mg/g	11-12 mg/g (23),
	11.06 (29);	(23); 14-36%	28-183% (25);
	129 g/kg(27)	(25); 27.10 mg/g	96 g/kg (27)
Black tea	17.8(22); 2-126	80.5-134.9 mg/g	22-28 mg/g (23);
	mg/g (28); 4.62	(23); 22.25 mg/g	23-49 mg/g (28)
	mg/g (29)	(29)	
Darjeeling tea	36.9 (22)		
Fruit tea	61.5 g/g (23)		
Tea flowers	10-38 mg/g (28)		3-8 mg/g (28)
Ceylon tea	47.5 (22)		

Note : The number within brackets indicate the References.

Fig. 1. Comparison of biochemicals of green tea and black tea.

content of the final product. Significantly higher content of caffeine in black tea may be due to the degree of fermentation during the manufacture.

Theaflavin and thearubigin :

TF, a class of tea polyphenols showed anticancer activity and the compounds like TF and TR were found to be responsible for tea qualities, increases with the increase of fermentation time^{30,31}. Attractive reddish/brownish colors of tea observed in a cup of tea were due to presence of TF and TR. Significantly higher amount of TR was found in black tea where as lower TF was found in green tea (Table 1). The contents of TF, TR and caffeine vary with localities and the patterns of variation change from clone to clone³³.

Polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase activity :

Highest amount of PPO and POD were found in green tea than black tea (Table 1). Black tea is obtained by a post-harvest fermentation which is an auto-oxidation reaction catalyzed by the enzyme polyphenol oxidase whereas green teas are steamed to inactive oxidation⁶. PPO and POD of tea extract showed a good inhibition on apple PPO and apple browning³³. Similarly natural inhibitor such as PPO and POD isolated from tea leaves prevent the browning of apple juice during pasteurization and beer turbidity during storage³⁴. The oxidation of green tea catechins by polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase gives rise to O-quinones and semiquinones respectively, whose instability, until now, have hindered the kinetic characterization of enzymatic oxidation of the catechins³⁵.

Superoxide dismutase-like activity :

Superoxide dismutase activity of green tea was found to be higher in green tea than black tea (Table 1). It may be due to presence of higher catechins or polyphenols. In addition to different catechins, significant amount of SOD present in green and black teas also contribute to the antioxidant activities. These enzymes also act as antioxidants, preventing radical formation and also converting existing hydroperoxyl radicals into stable oxygen and hydrogen peroxide. They eliminate the danger of radicals and prevent radical damage to the cell membrane. These protective enzymes (superoxide dismutase) are some proteins that swim in the membrane fluid around polysaturated fats and hence are in close proximity to them³⁶.

In conclusion, the present investigation provide useful information on total polyphenols, catechins, reducing sugar, theaflavin, thearubigin, polyphenol oxidase, peroxidase and superoxide dismutase-like activities of green tea and black tea. The above values of green tea were compared with black tea. The overall strength being in the order of green tea > black tea. Much higher content of polyphenols, catechins and enzyme activities of green tea have given evident that green tea is more potent than black tea.

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